

INFORMATION WARFARE AND DEMOCRACY: US STRATEGIES
AGAINST SOCIAL MEDIA WARFARE OF CHINA AND RUSSIA

Ahmad Nawaz

MPhil IR Scholar, Department of Political Science, University of the Punjab

malikadg123@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Ahmad Nawaz

Abstract

Democracies, like the US, face challenges in the cyber-era due to their openness which allows the easy free flow of information. Social media allows countries like China and Russia to target the strengths of a democracy – freedom of information and free speech. This leads the US to use defensive strategies on digital platforms to deal with growing threats of manipulation and propaganda. Most of the world’s tech giants, such as Meta and Google, are US-based, which helps the US strengthen its defensive strategies. Russia has used social media to spread propaganda against the USA for a long time, a major highlighted point came when Russia interfered in the US election in 2016. Russia uses aggressive strategies by using fake accounts and bots on social media to spread disinformation in order to tilt public opinion in its desired way. China’s strategies on social media in the past were less aggressive as compared to Russian strategies. However, a shift has been seen recently as China is increasing its activity of manipulation on digital platforms. In 2024, many sites linked with China were removed from Google Search for spreading fake news. The major objective of both China and Russia is to create distrust in the minds of people of the US against their system. Joseph S. Nye Jr. argues that digital propaganda comes under sharp power, and it is difficult for it to coexist with soft power. Therefore, the US must carefully counter China and Russia without damaging its own soft power.

INTRODUCTION

The perception of the public has always been important in politics throughout history. And with the digital age, it became very easy to shape it regardless of the fact wherever they live in the world. Cyberspace is the new battleground in international politics, and it is not limited to any physical boundary. Cyberspace refers to a virtual world, a space where anybody can interact with no physical boundary limitations. Social media, a

major part of cyberspace, has become very important in global affairs. Platforms like Facebook and Twitter hold the power to change the course of a whole region as seen during the Arab Spring. (Choucri, 2012)

In the world, a state needs its people on its side whether it is going to wage a war or simply for development. It can be understood from the ideas of Clausewitz and Douglas MacArthur who

emphasize the support of people for the state to flourish. And social media is considered important because in today's world, almost every adult has a smart phone with major social media applications installed on it. (King & Gallagher, 2021) According to Pew Research Center, smart phones are in the hands of 91 percent of US people. This figure tells us that nearly all the adult population is vulnerable to the propaganda of social media. And in today's digital war, militaries are not the major target, but the public is the real target, with the data being the most valuable thing. (Center, 2024)

Social media warfare has been long dominated by the US-Russia dynamics, but in recent times, a third big player China has entered it, making it a more complex triad. Russia is long accused of using social media to spread propaganda against its adversaries, mainly US. The approach of Russia on social media is an aggressive one with disruptive tactics while spreading false information. Russia often targets the entire system of country with propaganda in order to loosen the trust of the public in their system. And in the case of US, the target of Russia is weakening the democracy of US by creating confusion in the minds of about their system. And Russia usually becomes active during important events, for example the involvement of Russia in the US elections 2016. (Jakubowski, 2019) On the other hand, China has a less aggressive approach on social media as its plan it to slowly change the perception of the world in the future. And China is doing this by spreading and promoting the good side of its country with positive stories. While mostly praising its own country, China has also started showing itself better than the US and how US has been cruelled with the world, including in Middle East, but China only speaks the language of trade and economy. And China has also some strong social media platforms, including TikTok and WeChat, against the US-based social media companies. Meanwhile, China does not allow the information from the US to penetrate the minds of its people as it has strong firewall for internet. (Guo, 2023)

The US has majorly used the defensive approach on social media and in the current time, US is a

major target of the social media campaigns by Russia and China. The US, being a liberal democracy, has a very open system in which free speech and free media provide adversaries a loophole to penetrate. This also raises concerns about the shortcoming of openness and democracy in today's digital world. However, the US is dealing with this issue greatly given the fact that almost all the global major social media platforms are US-based. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube etc. have been cooperative allowing US to counter propaganda while remaining on the backfoot and not using much aggressive steps. (Helmus, et al., 2018)

This paper will explore the social media strategies of US, Russia, and China by addressing the following research questions:

- **Why does the US used defensive strategies in social media warfare, but Russia and China go towards offensive strategies?**
- **How US effectively deal with Russian and Chinese offensive tactics with its defensive approach?**

Methodology

This paper is qualitative research and it uses secondary data to explore the different approaches employed by US, Russia, and China on social media for shaping narrative. The secondary study relies on includes journal articles, books, reports from research organizations, news articles, and conference proceedings. By using these sources, this paper analyzes how US is using its cyber capabilities on social media to counter propaganda by Russia and China. And how the approaches of both Russia and China differ in using social media against US. Because this is qualitative research, the major focus will look at the deeper meaning of the steps taken by US, Russia and China. This will allow us to understand the complex triad relationship of these three countries in the war of social media to shape narratives. The main sources, journal articles and books, provide an understanding of the clash between the three nations based on history and the present situations. The reports and conference proceedings provide information about cyber power and different tactics being used on the

social media platforms. And news articles are used to include information on recent events in order to better understand the situation.

Theoretical Framework

This paper uses social constructivism theory to explain the reasons behind the different approaches used by US, Russia and China on social media to shape ideas. The theory of social constructivism explains that the reality of the world is based on what people perceive. Therefore, the major driving forces behind the behavior of a state are not only physical power but they are the ideas, values and their interaction with each other. (Wendt, 1995) This theory explains that the US defensive strategies on social media are influenced by its ideas and values of democracy and free speech. Therefore, US is countering its adversaries, Russia and China, in a more transparent manner by working with social media platforms to create secure environment rather than going for offensive or strict control measures. On the other side, the offensive approach from the Russia relates to its long-standing idea of seeing western democracies as a direct challenge to its own system. And the China's idea to rule the world in the future by shaping the narratives of the world by showing positive images and labeling itself better than US to fit its authoritarian model. (Finnemore, 1996)

Social constructivism helps us understand that the behavior of states is shaped by its interactions with others and the perception it creates from it. For example, the defensive strategy of US on social media is not particularly for the Russia and China but rather it is shaped by the idea that US is a protector of the democratic values. And this is the reason why US made its social media platforms label content of Russian and Chinese government on social media as "state-controlled media" posts. (Roozenbeek, 2024)

The importance and power of public opinion is highlighted by E.H. Carr in his book "**The Twenty Years' Crisis: 1919–1939.**" He argues that controlling opinions is a very important kind of power and it can provide support to countries, from both domestic and international public, for their actions. And by shaping the public opinion

in a certain direction, a state can even legitimize some of its questionable steps at both domestic and international levels. Carr also explained that this kind of power is a subtle one, but it can draw one of the most effective outcomes. (Carr, 1939) In the past, traditional media was seen very powerful and important tool for shaping the perception of the people but social media hold much more power. And powerful countries like US, Russia, China are using the most powerful narrative shaping tool in their own ways to show world selective pictures of the reality. (Filipec, 2019)

US Defensive Strategies on Social media

Most of the strategies of the US on social media are considered defensive in nature. The US is considered one of the most powerful states in the cyber domain, and that power of the US can be seen through its strong defense. US has always been vulnerable to the propaganda of the social media, and Russia was the main adversary of US on social media in the past. But, with the changing global dynamics, China is now seen also an important social media challenge for the US. The issue of propaganda from the Russian side does not come with the advent of social media, it was a major issue during the Cold War too. That was the reason President Eisenhower established United States Information Agency (USIA) so that the US could counter Soviet propaganda. (Prier, 2020)

Cyber Power of the US:

The one of the major reasons which allows and made sure US remain on the defensive end on social media is the cyber power of the US. The hold of US in the technological field is very evident to the world, that helps US to achieve its objectives on social media in a subtle way that it is not seen as an offensive steps. There has been a debate about a tool which can calculate or measure the cyber power of nations. The Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs of Kennedy School, Harvard published 2 reports using a metric to measure cyber power. And its latest report name "**National Cyber Power Index**", which came in 2022, measured multiple strengths of states in cyberspace to rank countries in cyber

power. And it ranked a total of 30 countries based on their cyber power in which US is ranked the most powerful state in the cyberspace followed by China and Russia. (Voo, Hemani, & Cassidy, 2022)

Cyber Defense Measures:

US has developed measures to use the approach called “Defend Forward” in which US tackle issues on cyberspace before they cause harm. For this, the US has developed agencies, one of which is US Cyber Command, in order to deal with the issue of cyber threats including the propaganda done on social media. For example, after the majorly highlighted incident of Russian intervention in the US elections 2016 through the shaping of narratives using social media, US enhanced its preemptive measures and before the mid elections of 2018, US Cyber Command caught many Russian troll farms, which spread the propaganda, and blocked them before the election. (Nguyen & Sparks, 2020)

And with the changing environment of cyberspace, the US is getting ready with Artificial Intelligence (AI) to further enhance its defensive capabilities on the social media. AI will become the most efficient tool in detecting any propaganda post as AI holds the ability to analyze large data sets, which in this case are the posts. (Security, 2023)

Apart from that, the US has increased collaboration with the technology companies in order to enhance their defense mechanism on social media. The US requires social media platforms to share sources behind the political advertisement and transparency in other content too. Other than that, the US has pushed companies to take strict actions against social media propaganda. And there have been millions of accounts removed post 2016 US elections from the major platforms such as Facebook and Twitter. The Department of Home Security is playing a key role in working with social media companies. It can catch threats faster and can provide quick response to tackle propaganda instead of social media companies independently handling it. (Haigh, Haigh, & Kozak, 2018)

Use of Established Social Media Against Adversaries:

Although the US has a defensive approach, it also sometimes uses social media to spread a bad image of its adversaries. And that step too is backed by the fact that major social media companies are from the US which makes the narrative building easy. After the start of conflict between Ukraine and Russia, US has utilized its social media power to present Russia as a cruel state with cruel and inhumane leadership. The US news channels used social media channels with specific wording of the news of this conflict so that not only the public of US, but the global public see Russia as wrong. For example, New York Times shares photos on the conflict on Telegram with emotional captions by saying that Russia tortured Ukrainians captives and does not care of human rights. Similarly, US news channels are spreading negative image of China on social media by highlighting its human rights violations. The step of US indicates to its adversaries that US not just holds the capability of narrative building but its way of doing is more sophisticated which is seen not as offensive. Therefore, countries like Russia and China have to be very conscious of this weapon of the US. (Shevchenko, 2022)

Offensive Social Media Tactics by Adversaries Russian Offensive Strategies:

Russia has been long associated with the aggressive social media strategy. The importance of narrative was learned by Russia in a hard way with the disintegration of the USSR. Russia understood that one of the major causes of its fall was the narrative of its adversary, US, was bought by many countries compared to its narrative which fell short in catching more people. Therefore, it is one of the major reasons that Russia constantly attack US image through social media as it believes it is linked with its own image. The more the US image goes down, the more chances will be created for the Russia to enhance its position. Russia has always seen social media from a skeptical eye and believes CIA has created it to have an upper hand in the war of perception, even Putin has said the same. (Nocetti, 2015)

Russia is not new in propaganda campaigns; it has been doing this since the Cold War. During the Cold War, the KGB (Soviet intelligence agency) used multiple measures for propaganda in order to shape the narrative of the people around the world. Soviets used to attack important US personalities to spread the negative image of the country. For example, in 1960s, US Senator Barry Goldwater was portrayed as racist before the presidential elections and similarly Ronald Reagan was shown inhumane and pro-war person to affect his re-election campaign. However, the USSR did not have much success compared to the US in their narrative building campaigns as it lost the narrative war and got disintegrated. But the propaganda 2.0 of Russia, which is through social media, is much stronger. (Jones, 2019)

Evolved Russian Strategies and Social Media:

The strategies of Russia on social media are influenced by the some of the past events. Since US is an adversary of Russia for a long, therefore Russia has studied the strategies of US to create its social media strategy. Firstly, during the start of the Cold War, the US had nuclear weapons which held enough power to overpower the much larger conventional Soviet forces. What US did at that time was rather than competing with Soviets in a field where competition is hard, US used something else to counter. Similarly, in recent times, Russia understands it cannot compete with US in terms of armed forces or defense budget, but can fight in a new space, that is the cyberspace. Secondly, during the later stage of the Cold War, the US was more prone towards creating advanced weapons technology which can hit specific targets with more precision, e.g. Maneuverable Reentry Vehicles (MaRVs). Similarly, Russia is using social media, which is more cost effective, to target specific population with precise propaganda. Russia effectively presents the desired information to a specific population to have better results. These lessons showed Russia the way to the road of propaganda using social media as the power of social media was seen by the Russia during Arab Spring (McGeehan, 2018)

The point when Russian social media propaganda came into the limelight was the 2016 US

Presidential elections. Russia was accused of interfering in the elections through social media using bots, fake accounts, and hashtags to spread propaganda against one of the candidates whose name is Harry Clinton. Russia was accused of making the WikiLeaks of emails, which were harmful to Clinton campaign, go viral in order to weaken her chances of winning. And people believed that Russia is doing this because the other candidate, Donald Trump, is backed by Russia and it wants him to win. However, the actual reason was much bigger than this which world understood a lot later. Russia was doing all this not to make a certain candidate win, but to make a sense of doubt in the US public against their system and democracy. Because the objective of Russia against US is to portray its system as weak in front of its public as well as the world through any event. (Mejias & Vokuev, 2017)

The attacks by Russia on social media increased during the Russia-Ukraine conflict of 2014 as well as 2022. During the 2014 conflict, Russia used social media to make US look the actual cause of the conflict. Using fake accounts to spread propaganda, Russia backed the narrative that US involvement in the domestic politics of Ukraine is causing all this chaos. US was accused of supporting people against the pro-Russian government in order to bring the pro-Western government so that NATO could expand. Russian social media campaign also highlighted the role of US in the Middle East and how it created uncertainty in the whole region by interfering in the domestic matters of the states in the region. All this campaign by Russia gave it a way to somehow justify the annexation of Crimea. (Gerber & Zavisca, 2016)

The spread the narrative that US is backing an illegitimate government in Ukraine and used term "fascist junta" (which means illegal coup). Even Russia tried to show the public through social media that the US backed regime of Ukraine is just like the Islamic extremist groups such as Islamic State (IS). But the real question is how Russia was doing all that on the social media? The answer for that question is that Russia impersonated famous pro-Ukrainian websites plus used veterans' groups of Ukraine to show that the

information that people are seeing is true. (Treyger, Cheravitch, & Cohen, 2019)

And during the recent 2022 Russia-Ukraine Conflict, Russia took the help of social media to show its actions legitimate by creating narrative against US. The Russian strategy, in this war, was the denial of truth which is followed by distraction strategy. And to strengthen the campaign, Russia increased engagement on each of its posts which was shared for the propaganda. Fake likes and shares on the posts by bots made it look like to public that this post is saying the truth. Because psychologically, our brains do not question a post which contain a lot of likes, comments and shares therefore Russia applied this tactic. Russia tried to keep the tactics in this war more precise and it can be seen by the provided example. During the 77th session of the General Assembly, in which Russian aggression in Ukraine was criticized, Russia kept a close eye on this session and started spreading the view that Russia is a peacekeeper state while also spreading issues of UN to strengthen its state's image. (Baloyi, Mahlasela, Siphambili, & Stegmann, 2024)

Lastly, during the COVID-19 crisis, Russia spread this narrative on social media that Russia's vaccine, known as Sputnik V, is better option than western vaccines. This move was to show that western democracies, especially US, were unable to tackle this crisis the way Russia did. That means, indirectly Russia was trying to discredit the US system so that American people think the Russian system is better in dealing with crisis. Hence it will lead to hopelessness in the US people about their system. (Walter & Ophir, 2023)

Chinese Offensive Strategies:

The Chinese way of using social media for propaganda is different from Russia. Because unlike Russia, the aim of China is not just to spread short term disinformation for disruption any specific event like conflict. China is playing a very long-term game therefore it has more structured strategy of social media. Its strategy is long-term narrative building by shaping the public opinion in a subtle way so that in future it can undermine the credibility of other states, particularly its biggest hurdle for global

dominance which is USA. In other words, China's aim to shape the global public opinion to make generational impact by making the future generation of policy makers into its favor. This idea aligns with the remarks of Jack Lew, US ambassador to Israel, that the current generation have not seen founding of Israel, or the early wars middle east fought with it, but they are born in this time and only saw recent crisis in which Israel is more aggressive. Therefore, it would not be wrong to say that China is aiming to build its soft power in future by using social media tactics in current time. Social media is a part of broader goal of China that is "cognitive warfare" to shape the perceived image of the world. (Baughman & Singer, 2023)

China is spreading a narrative to portray itself as a peaceful country who does not want any violence meanwhile indicating that US has always been a violent country. Amitai Etzioni explained a similar concept in his book "Security First: For a Muscular, Moral Foreign Policy" that threats no longer cause by clash of civilizations but by views of the world. These views are divided into violent and non-violent, and many argue US must go with non-violent. But what China is doing through social media is to use this strategy is reverse by talking some violent steps on social media to show us as violent while portraying itself as non-violent. (Etzioni, 2007)

Narrative Building of China:

Domestically, China has created a very strict controlled over the social media as applications like WeChat (alternative of WhatsApp), Rednote (alternative of Instagram), Weibo (alternative of X) are used to keep check on people. That way, China makes sure that the content consumed by the public is completely monitored and remove content that it against the state, for example, if a post mentioned words like pro-democracy protest, it will be removed. China has one of the stronger digital firewalls which do not let any foreign content penetrate the country. Particularly, China does not allow content from US-based platforms within its boundaries so that no western perspective reach the local public. That way, China is able to provide modified versions of

western news to its public to shape their perception in any direction. (Agustine, 2024)

Figure 1. Chinese alternative social media platforms

China even has group of people, known as Fifty Cent Party, which are estimated to be between 500,000 to 2 million people. They are assigned to spread pro-state content on social media to keep the public distracted from real issues. They are called fifty cent party because each is paid 50 Chinese cent (RMB¥ 0.50) on each post they spread on in the favor of Chinese government. Major part of this group operates on domestic social media networks to counter the influence of the west, especially US, but some portion also works at the international level. They use global social media platforms like Facebook, X (Twitter), Reddit, TikTok etc. They use global platforms to enhance the positive image of China while undermining trust of people against their democratic systems especially US. (King, Pan, & Roberts, 2017) Meanwhile during the US elections, China shows democracy of US as problematic by spreading information like political fights and controversies of elections. Hence, we can say China has dual-use policy, degrading the soft power of US on international level as well among the domestic people. That way, China is crafting a way to future in which US do

not have people support from all parts of the world. (IISS, 2022)

The importance of social media for the China can be seen from the fact that the army of China, known as People's Liberation Army (PLA), views social media as a major part of the battlefield. Many argued that China is learning this from USA that how importance soft power holds in the international system therefore they are aiming to shape the people's perception. PLA has been studying cognitive warfare for a long time. This form of warfare is not only limited to spreading disinformation but has multiple factors involved in it. Some of these include using psychological manipulation, controlling perceptions, spreading propaganda, playing with emotions etc. in order to enhance your own image while weakening the image of your adversary. For example, China uses its accounts, CCTN or Global Times, to spread narratives to portray the actions of China in the South China Sea as legitimate, while also showing the US backed rivals, Vietnam and Philippines, as the real aggressors in this region. The technique used here is also similar to what China does on the domestic level, that is spreading too much

information in their own favor that many people believe it is a true information. (Langlois-Berthelot & Bazalgette, 2023)

• **Summit for Democracy** hosted by US in the 2021 led China to use social media campaign against US. More than 100 leaders around the world were invited to this summit by the President Biden and Chinese President was not one of them. This was taken seriously by China, and it was seen spreading anti-US narratives on social media. Two of the famous hashtags were circulated which were “#WhatIsDemocracy” and “#WhoDefinesDemocracy”. In campaign, China used layered approach which means China utilized multiple type of accounts for greater impact. This includes the use of bot networks, real accounts with manipulated posts, and even state-sponsored accounts. What this campaign did was

to show that democratic system, which US promotes, is full of flaws and the Chinese system is more stable and efficient. Multiple issues of the US were highlighted including protests (2021 Capitol riots), racial inequality, weakness of US, regime change in the name of democracies, interventions in multiple countries etc. And many people from countries who do not have good relations with US joined this campaign too. Many argued that this digital media can provide countries with different kinds of opportunities like the one China utilized by promoting its authoritarian regime a viable alternative. China even used cartoons to discredit US democracy which were shared across the internet, mainly social media. Below are some examples of the posts shared on social media against the US during the Summit for Democracy. (Jacobs & Carley, 2023)

Figure 2. Facebook post by former spokesman for the Ministry of Foreign Affairs

Figure 3. Tweet by Global Times

Chinese Information Warfare and Cyber Attacks:

One might think that social media propaganda and cyber attacks are two different things, but they also work together to achieve goals on social media. China uses cyber espionage with social media information sharing in order to discredit the credibility of the US system. First China uses multiple hacking techniques through which it gathers sensitive information of US. The data which is stolen by hacking is then used to shape public opinion using social media. Cyberattacks has been used as the foundation which allow China to spread its messages on social media. One of the famous groups, also highlighted by US Department of Justice, is the APT41. This group does not target specific individuals but rather government agencies and big corporations. This

group mostly works using tricks like sending fake emails, putting in malware and breaching networks. These attacks come under the category of espionage, and then China use the stolen information in order to enhance the social media operations. This group is also involved in working against the US backed allies like Taiwan. During the 2024 elections of Taiwan, information was spread on social media platforms against the pro-independence candidate. Here too the information was first stolen through espionage from the research institute affiliated with the government of Taiwan. In the same manner, this group stole information of US in order to make the general public of the USA against its own system so that the democracy, a power of US, becomes less acceptable in world. (Clarke, D Ormrod, & Slay, 2023)

Combined Use of Cyberattack and Social Media by China

Stage	Action	Goal
Cyberattack	Steal sensitive data from US institutions	Gather information for narrative building campaigns.
Sharing Information	Using social media to spread stolen data	Portraying negative picture adversary.
Spread of Propaganda	Using bots and fake accounts.	Promote Chinese narrative and hide own negative points.
Narrative Control	Floods social media with pro-state messages.	Change competing views and control public views

Comparative Analysis of Social Media Measures of US vs Russia and China

US: Learning from the Past:

The US has been prone to multiple foreign propagandas which were targeted to manipulate the opinion of its public. And one of the major reasons for that is the power which people hold in its democracy and openness. This is the reason why its adversaries are interested in spreading specific narratives in the public as they know that these people are the ones who select government. (LBJ, 2021) One of the prominent scholars, Joseph S. Nye Jr., wrote multiple writings on the soft power and role of social media. Nye explained the concept of “sharp power”, first use by Christopher Walker and Jessica Ludwig, to tell why offensive steps on the social media does not favor a state in long run. He argued that sharp power, that is to manipulate through tools like disinformation, fake news, and other covert ways to cause harm, is more towards hard power than soft power. Reason being soft power is the one in which culture and ideas are spread to persuade others. And Nye argues that sharp power does not increase soft power rather decreases it as it often damages that one state who is using it. Therefore, in the current time of social media, the US must not lose its position from defensive approach to offensive. The same thing is being adapted by China to some extent as China avoids using too disruptive tactics as Russia do in order to not damage its reputation. (Jr., 2019)

US, by learning from past, was ready with its defensive approach on social media during the start of Ukraine crisis. In this, Russia was, as discussed before, accused of spreading false information on the social media to portray its

image as positive one meanwhile discrediting the image of US and its democracy. Since Russia was not only targeting US with false news but also NATO, therefore US decided to improve its defense with the help of NATO. And used **allied countermeasures** as the US State Department worked with the European governments to spread the factual information using multiple official channels of both Europe and US. Ukraine was also provided help by US in the cybersecurity domain to strengthen its capabilities. (Beecroft, 2022) These step from US were taken in both Ukraine Crisis of 2016 and 2022. And to further enhance the defence, an online site was created by both US and European Union in order to enhance public awareness as well as to make it easy for the world to catch any wrong information or facts. (Schuette, 2023)

US uses specific words for its campaign against propaganda to look less aggressive. For instance, US uses words like Public Diplomacy (PD) for its steps, which are mostly defensive and very few offensive, to counter propaganda (Jr., Protecting Democracy in an Era of Cyber Information War, 2019). The official documents of the US accept the seriousness of the propaganda issue spread through social media. The rapid rise of social media brought another term, specifically for social media, which is Public Diplomacy 2.0 (PD 2.0). And based on the idea of PD 2.0, US is aiming to enhance the strength of its information channels and catch the accounts and the websites to remove them from multiple platforms. In the last of 2024, US caught and removed hundreds of websites linked to China which are spreading fake news. These were removed from the Google Search which put the narrative into the minds of people

to make them share posts on social media naturally the way China wants. One thing that can be seen here is that the defense of US becomes stronger because most major tech giants are US-based companies. Here too, Google, a US-based company, helped US removed certain websites from its search engine. (Woollacott, 2024)

US has been long utilizing its upper hand of having most of global social media being US-based. US did a major crackdown against the accounts, backed by China, used for the spread of false information mostly on platforms like Facebook and X (Twitter). In this crackdown, thousands of accounts were caught by US with the help of Facebook and X (Twitter) itself. Most of these fake accounts and bots were used to spread narrative against US on issues like COVID-19, problems of US democracy, and even on the negative role of US in Taiwan crisis. (Jacobs & Carley, 2023)

Russian vs Chinese Social Media Tactics:

Both of the states, Russia and China, consider social media as an important tool to shape the perception of public in order to control it. However, there is major difference in the approaches of both countries as their goals from social media are different. Russia is more prone to short-term goals with more chaos and disruption content on the social media. On the other hand, China is working on a longer vision of having the world on its side in the coming times. Therefore, Chinese social media propaganda against US is to slowly change the perception of the general public of the US. The difference of both can be analyzed by the actions they have taken on social media.

Firstly, the Russian approach, which is a short-term one, is associated with the strategy known as **fire of falsehood**. This strategy means sharing a lot of false information so that the public become so overwhelmed that it could not figure out what to believe and what to not. This strategy is the backbone of the Russian motives of causing divisions within the democratic states. The same trick was used during the 2016 US elections as Russia spread messages to different groups to make them against each other more. Russia most of the times tries to deepen divisions within

societies, as it does with US society. So that the general public may lose trust in their own system. Therefore, the goal of Russia is not to make itself seen a good country or a country having good system but to make the people of US so confused that it becomes harder to understand anything in their system. And it will weaken the democracy of US and its allies while making people distracted of Russia's problems.

On the other hand, the strategy of China is a long-term one in which China is playing a very slow game. China is not interested in creating chaotic situation with the bombardment of fake news, rather China is slowing promoting the positive side of it around the globe against the US to indicate what narrative US spread about China is not the actual case. Even during the Covid-19 pandemic, China was seen successfully alter the damage to its image mostly done by western media by blaming China for the spread of virus. China not only spread the narrative to the world that the vaccine it created is the best, even better than western vaccines. (Ellis, Piazza, Greer, & Uribe, 2022) Also, China showed the world that it has tackled the pandemic better than the US, even in the trade aspect. And the success of China can be seen from the remarks of renowned Francis Fukuyama, who also highlighted that China's response to pandemic was better than the West. (Fukuyama, 2020)

While understanding the difference between the two countries and their different approaches on social media, a direct comparison is needed to better grasp it. Russia, in comparison to China, has less resources and less economic influence on the which simply makes it harder to control the global narrative. Therefore, it is more viable for the Russia to use the quick approach of using fake information campaign in major events like elections, geopolitical crisis etc. But China has the strong influence in the global market because of its financial power which allow it to play a more subtle and safer game on social media. Therefore, China is more interested in investing for its soft power on social media for the gradual increase in the soft power. (Excellence, 2015)

Russian vs Chinese Social Media Tactics

Aspect	Russian Tactics	Chinese Tactics
Focus	Short-term disruption	Long-term approach to shape narrative
Methods	Troll farms, bots, fake news	State-sponsored influencers
Platforms	Facebook, Twitter	TikTok, WeChat
Objective	Discrediting democracies	Promotion of positive image of China
Target Audience	Groups within democracies	Global audience

Assessing the Impact of US Strategies:

The US has been taking multiple measures to counter social media disinformation, especially from adversaries Russia and China. And these social media defensive measures by US have both successes and some challenges. If we look at how and why it is successful in more cases, one major reason will always be the fact that major social media are US-based, and it makes the collaboration between them and US government easier. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube easily allow US government to detect content that is spreading propaganda and these platforms also removes it. This single thing is the backbone of US defensive strategies as it knows

that social media is dominated by US therefore it will not have to make much hassle of going offensive to deal with adversaries while doing the same on the backfoot. And that is way, in the recent times, many major platforms of social media have started labeling posts as state-controlled media which are done by social media handles like CGTN (China) or RT (Russia). And this step does not let any information from these major social media handles manipulate the public as people do not take information from these channels as seriously as they used to do. Regulating. (Bradshaw, Elswah, & Perini, 2024)

Figure 4. China & Russian social media accounts labelled as state-controlled media but not BBC & VOA

These same social media platforms of the US have been removing the social media handles detected of spreading false information. For example, multiple steps were taken during the US elections of 2020 in which US-based social media platforms removed posts/accounts spreading wrong information, mostly linked with either China or Russia. Apart from removing them, platforms also started labeling posts with wrong information which making it easy for the public to not get caught by any false or wrong information. (Bradshaw, Grossman, & McCain, An investigation of social media labeling decisions preceding the 2020 U.S. election, 2023)

It is important to note that all this could not have been done only by US-based social media companies but US agencies were also required to work in this domain. And the effectiveness of US defensive strategies on social media is made possible by the US agencies such as US Cyber Command and Department of Homeland Security which worked with the social media platforms to tackle the issue of cyber propaganda. (Nguyen & Sparks, 2020)

However, there are still some limitations for the US in dealing with the social media propaganda from China and Russia. Although major social media platforms are US-based but in recent times other social media platforms has become popular, such as TikTok (Linked with China), and US cannot investigate or gather information from these platforms. This is creating a new dilemma for the US on whether to let these types of platforms work in the US or not and to what extent surveillance can be done on these platforms. (Tian, et al., 2024)

Another major issue is the adaptation of new techniques by China and Russia on social media. They are using state media less and proxy social media channels more. They are hiring, sometimes staying on the front foot and sometimes back, social media handles to subtly spread information for them. Not just that, China and Russia also approaching local influencers of countries like US to make them spread their narrative in exchange of some money. Therefore, as social media is expanding, control is getting out of the hands of the US and major issues are being created. (Josh A. Goldstein, 2024)

Overall, the US has still managed to take a hold on situation because of its strong capabilities from social media platforms and its strong agencies but the tide is shifting and there is need of some reforms in order to deal with the propaganda issue.

Conclusion

The cyberspace has become the new battleground of conflict for the major powers like US, Russia, and China. Major powers are using social media with different approaches to shape the narratives of the people. The US is considered the most powerful state in cyberspace, but its approach on social media is defensive to deal with the propaganda of the adversaries. The US has a strong soft image in the world and a leading country of liberal democracy therefore it cannot risk using those offensive tactics which may damage its image. On the other side, Russia is often seen using offensive tactics, especially during major events, to create chaos in order to weaken the trust of the US public in their system. Russian offensive approach was evident during events like US elections, COVID-19, Ukraine conflicts (2014 and 2022). But the approach of China is, while being offensive, a subtle one in which China's major focus is to show how good China is compared to US in order to set the ground for the future superpower. The US has seen effectively tackling both of its adversaries on social media with its major hold on the internet and effective agencies. However, the tide is shifting as the Russia and China are taking new steps and instead of using state media, they are outsourcing companies and people.

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